

Conference Abstract

Morphological characterization of *Umbra krameri* and its current and potential invasive competitors in Hungary

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Abstract

The European mudminnow (*Umbra krameri*) is the only representative of its genus in the Palearctic region. According to the literature, its evolutionary lineage diverged from its closest North American relatives (*U. limi* and *U. pygmaea*) over 60 million years ago. Although it was formerly widespread in the Middle and Lower Danube regions, the species has undergone a significant decline in recent decades. Its populations are primarily threatened by habitat loss and degradation, as well as the spread of non-native fish species. In this presentation, we describe the morphological and morphometric characteristics of *U. krameri*, with particular emphasis on the variability of these traits across different populations, conservation-, and evolutionarily significant units. Furthermore, we highlight the key morphological and morphometric features of the species' most important current and potential invasive competitors -especially the two Nearctic *Umbra* species - which may aid species identification during field sampling (Suppl. material 1).

Presenting author

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Supplementary material

Suppl. material 1: Morphological characterization of *Umbra krameri* and its current and potential invasive competitors in Hungary [doi](#)

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